

Data-driven elastoplastic constitutive modelling with physics-informed RNNs using the Virtual Fields Method for indirect training

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for accurate material behaviour data in engineering simulations has exposed the limitations of traditional constitutive models. Although recent advances in full-field measurement techniques provide more detailed material characterization, conventional approaches still heavily rely on explicit assumptions and labour-intensive experimentation. This paper revisits the indirect training methodology introduced by the authors [1], which integrates Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) with Gated-Recurrent Units (GRUs) and the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) to model material behaviour without labelled data. The earlier study demonstrated the feasibility of training a GRU-based RNN using only global force and strain data through the VFM. Building on those findings, this work presents a more robust approach featuring an improved network architecture, with residual connections to enhance gradient flow and training stability, while also incorporating physics-based constraints. Extensive hyperparameter tuning was conducted to optimize the model and a sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the impact of the virtual fields on the accuracy and training dynamics. The models were validated using additional heterogeneous mechanical tests and the Reconstructed Axial Force Ratio (RAFR), as a key performance indicator, to further assess the physical correctness. The results show enhanced predictive accuracy and improved force reconstruction when larger sets of virtual fields are employed. Additionally, normalizing the VFM loss contributed to more consistent predictions and force reconstruction across all time stages. Stress contour plots further confirm the model's ability to accurately predict stress distributions, which are in good agreement with the reference, with low median and average absolute errors.

1. Introduction

The widespread adoption of numerical simulation software in the engineering field has increased the need for precise material behaviour data [2,3]. In Finite Element Analysis (FEA) software, the material behaviour is implemented in a constitutive model. Conventionally, these models are derived from physical knowledge and phenomenological observations. However, the behaviour

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observed in simple one-strain-state mechanical tests is often generalized [4,5]. Moreover, the resulting constitutive equations contain empirical parameters that need to be calibrated [5].

In the past, the calibration process was limited to homogeneous deformation data due to the lack of high-resolution measurement equipment and restrictions to the specimens' geometries. As such, complex models often required an extensive number of experiments, making the whole process expensive and time-consuming [6]. In recent years, those limitations were overcome with the introduction of Digital Image Correlation (DIC) techniques, allowing the extraction of heterogeneous multi-axial displacement fields at numerous measurement points. Such capabilities unlocked the development of new mechanical specimens able to generate material behaviour data with higher levels of heterogeneity (e.g. [7–10], among others), and opening the door to the so-called Material Testing 2.0 (MT2.0) paradigm [11]. DIC also enabled more sophisticated approaches for the inverse identification of constitutive parameters, such as the Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) [12] and the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) [13]. Despite these advancements, constitutive parameter identification remains difficult and very model-dependent. Moreover, the phenomenological nature of the conventional constitutive models means their explicit form is fundamentally biased due to the simplifying assumptions of first-order principles [14]. Therefore, these models will always be constrained by their mathematical formulations.

The unprecedented growth recently experienced in the various domains of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) has led to the growing adoption of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) across a wide variety of fields. Within the field of material modelling, ANNs can potentially lead to a paradigm shift in the sense that they do not require any assumptions about an explicit form, effectively eliminating the need for parameter identification [15,16]. Furthermore, ANNs can handle the high volumes of data obtained from full-field measurements and are able to learn patterns implicitly, thus mitigating the biases inherent to conventional constitutive laws [14]. ANN-based constitutive modelling was first explored by Ghaboussi et al. [17], who demonstrated promising results with a Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN) trained to capture the cyclic behaviour of concrete. An early application to metal behaviour is attributed to Furukawa and Yagawa [18], who extended the concept to viscoplasticity using a state-space representation. Notable foundational works also include the implementation of an ANN material into a FEA solver [19] and the introduction of an analytical tangent stiffness matrix for ANN-based material models [20].

Plasticity is hard to model with ANNs due to history-dependent phenomena. Simple architectures are unable to capture them, as there is no mechanism that relates the inputs in the current time step with the outputs from previous time steps [21,22]. In earlier applications, the issue was somewhat circumvented by supplying stress and strain tensors from previous time steps, with additional internal variables of the constitutive model, as input features to a FFNN to predict the material response [18,23,24]. The approach resulted in added complexity and the reliance on internal variables meant resorting to assumptions about the explicit form of the constitutive law. Moreover, internal variables often lack direct physical meaning and are generally not accessible through standard experiments. Nonetheless, exceptions exist in specific modelling frameworks, such as crystal plasticity [25]. Further advancements in computational resources, allowed the development of more sophisticated network architectures, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). Contrary to FFNNs, RNNs are particularly robust for implicit constitutive modelling due to built-in memory cells that capture the effects of path-dependent behaviour [26]. Using sequences of strain tensors spanning from a number of time stages in the past up to the current time stage t , a RNN can capture the temporal dependencies, allowing to predict the corresponding stress state accurately. Such capabilities had resulted in a variety of works reported in the field [1,21,22,27–31].

Most works reported on ANN-based constitutive modelling follow a supervised learning paradigm that relies on labelled data pairs, usually strain and stress. However, the latter is not measurable in experiments based on complex heterogeneous mechanical specimens. Even from simple uniaxial homogeneous tests, stress is obtained from indirect calculations and assumptions, such as theoretical boundary conditions. In a context where real experimental data is used to train the ANN model, the training process must be carried out indirectly. This reality imposes that the training dataset must contain measurable variables only, such as displacements and/or strains and global force. During training, the variable to predict is indirectly obtained from intermediate calculations.

Within the framework of indirect training a few contributions have been found in the literature. Xu et al. [32] proposed predicting the Cholesky factors of the tangent stiffness, with the stress tensor being computed from intermediate steps. The model provided numerically stable solutions, albeit only for the non-linear segment of the material response. Both Huang et al. [33] and Xu et al. [34] proposed to replace the constitutive model in a FEA solver by an ANN, and imposed physical constraints during training. Similarly, Liu et al. [35] proposed a coupled mechanical system through the integration of an ANN with FEA. These approaches are analogous to FEMU and, while the physical correctness the ANN solutions is guaranteed, the drawbacks are (i) the need to write a FEA code based on an automatic differentiation package (e.g., Pytorch or TensorFlow), making the finite element step time-consuming; (ii) multiple FEA simulations have to be run per epoch, making the training computationally demanding. Benady et al. [36] developed a method based on the minimization of the modified constitutive relation error (mCRE) in order to train physics-augmented neural networks to learn thermodynamic potentials and constitutive laws using only partial strain or displacement measurements, without stress data. The proposed method demonstrated high noise robustness and minimal sensitivity to user-defined hyperparameters with training databases sufficiently diverse in terms of loading cases. In the domain of hyperelasticity, Huang et al. [33] showed that an ANN could be made thermodynamically consistent by predicting the hyperelastic energy instead of the stress tensor, which was computed via automatic differentiation. In an earlier work, Man and Furukawa [37] also used an energy-based loss function to indirectly train an ANN. Thakolkaran et al. [4] opted for an ensemble of Input Convex Neural Networks (ICNNs) to learn the constitutive response of a set of well-known hyperelastic constitutive models, resorting only to full-field data. Still in the framework of hyperelasticity, in a recent work by Jeong et al. [38], an ensemble of four independent Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) was employed to extract the material behaviour from full-field data, with physical constraints being encoded within a multi-objective loss. Despite promising results shown from the last two approaches, training multiple ANN models concurrently

makes the process harder, computationally demanding and adds complexity to model selection tasks (e.g. hyperparameter tuning). On another recent work in the domain of hyperplasticity, Franke et al. [39] employed an advanced energy–momentum scheme for time discretization to improve the performance of a Physics-Augmented Neural Network (PANN) in dynamical simulations, ensuring energy and momentum conservation. The authors reported excellent results, however it is not clear their approach is applicable to real experimental data. Finally, notable contributions by Flaschel et al. were aimed at the unsupervised discovery of the explicit form of the yield surface of a certain category of materials [40] and its extension to a general class of materials [41]. These approaches ensure physically consistent solutions, however, the authors still resort to several assumptions about the existence of internal history variables and the explicit formulations of the models.

In a previous paper, the authors proposed a quite innovative indirect training methodology which involved coupling the VFM with a GRU-based RNN model for material modelling [1]. The method allows using the global force and strain data to indirectly train the neural network, with the equilibrium being evaluated globally through the VFM loss function. The key advantages highlighted by the authors were (i) the computational efficiency gained from bypassing the use of FEA, (ii) the compatibility with both full-field measurements and numerically generated data and (iii) the independence of the boundary conditions. The possibility of using the VFM to train an ANN was then proven to be feasible through transfer learning. In the current paper, the authors revisit the proposed indirect training method, (i) employing a new RNN model, with a more robust architecture, (ii) trained from scratch using user-defined virtual fields and (iii) a mixture of soft and hard constraints based on general constitutive requirements. A more streamlined validation procedure is also adopted, based on different heterogeneous mechanical specimens, an external key performance indicator (KPI) and a simulation performed with the implementation of the trained RNN model in a FEA solver.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the theoretical background related to general elastoplastic behaviour and provides an overview of the requirements for constitutive equations that were implemented as constraints for ANN training. In Section 3, the VFM is introduced as well as its theoretical background. The coupled RNN-VFM indirect training methodology is also presented. In Section 4, RNNs with gated recurrent units (GRUs) are introduced along with the corresponding mathematical background. The chosen network architecture, as well as the data generation, training and validation procedures, are detailed in Section 5. Finally, in Section 6, results from hyperparameter tuning are presented, as well as, the influence of different virtual fields on the training dynamics is explored. The results obtained with the best model on validation data and the corresponding FEA implementation are also discussed.

2. Material modelling

2.1. Elastoplasticity

The classical constitutive laws governing elastoplasticity feature a transition between elastic and plastic regimes. A material undergoes elastic deformation until the initial yield stress σ_0 is reached, beyond which irreversible plastic deformation takes place along with hardening phenomena. The transition is governed by an yield function:

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, p) \leq 0, \quad (1)$$

which depends on the stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and the accumulated plastic strain p . Under plasticity, the stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ remains on the yield surface ($f = 0$) due to the hardening parameters, while $f \leq 0$ under elastic deformation. Hence, the strain can be assumed to be additively decomposed as follows [42]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p. \quad (2)$$

Hence, an effective plastic strain rate can be defined, as follows:

$$\dot{p} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} (\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p), \quad (3)$$

leading to the accumulated plastic strain p being obtained as:

$$p = \int \dot{p} dt. \quad (4)$$

The hypoelastic constitutive relation maps the elastic strain to the stress through the tangent stiffness tensor \mathbf{C} as [43]:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e. \quad (5)$$

The plastic flow follows the normality condition [19,44]:

$$d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p = d\lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}, \quad (6)$$

forcing the increment in the plastic strain to occur in the normal direction to the tangent of the yield surface at the load point [45]. The plastic multiplier $d\lambda$ is derived from the hardening rule after employing the consistency condition $f = df = 0$ [44]. The

constitutive relation from Eq. (5) can then be rewritten in the general form [32]:

$$\dot{\sigma} = \mathbf{H}\dot{\epsilon} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{C}\dot{\epsilon} & \text{for } f < 0 \\ \left[\mathbf{C} - \frac{\left(\mathbf{C} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right) \left(\mathbf{C} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right)^T}{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right)^T \left(\mathbf{C} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right)} \right] \dot{\epsilon} & \text{for } f = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{H} is a general tangent stiffness tensor that degenerates into the elastic tangent stiffness \mathbf{C} under elasticity. For more details concerning these formulations the reader is advised to refer to Dunne and Petrinic [42].

2.2. Requirements for constitutive equations

2.2.1. Laws of thermodynamics

The laws of thermodynamics impose two constraints on stress–strain relationships. The first law requires that the work done by stress must either be stored as recoverable internal energy in the solid or dissipated as heat [43]. As such, a local entropy generation, or intrinsic dissipation in the material is defined, such that:

$$\gamma_{\text{loc}} = \sigma : \dot{\epsilon} + \theta \dot{\eta} - \dot{E}, \quad (8)$$

where σ is the stress tensor, $\dot{\epsilon}$ the strain rate tensor, θ the absolute temperature, η the entropy per unit volume and E the internal energy per unit volume. The second law of thermodynamics requires that, if a sample of material is subjected to a cycle of deformation, starting and ending with identical strain and internal energy, the total work must be positive or zero, such that [3,43,46]:

$$\gamma_{\text{loc}} \geq 0. \quad (9)$$

A requirement that stems from the second law of thermodynamics is that the plastic power must be non-negative, in the absence of damage and heat conduction, i.e. [47]:

$$\dot{w}^{\text{p}} = \sigma : \dot{\epsilon}^{\text{p}} \geq 0. \quad (10)$$

A negative plastic dissipation would imply a decrease in temperature as a result of inelastic deformation, which would violate the second law of thermodynamics. Hence, plastic dissipation must remain non-negative and non-decreasing because it represents irreversibly lost energy. From here, it naturally follows that the accumulated plastic work

$$w^{\text{p}} = \int_0^t \dot{w}^{\text{p}} dt, \quad (11)$$

should be non-decreasing [47]. However, since plastic work includes both plastic dissipation and plastic free energy, such condition may not always be verified [48]. For example, in the event of reverse loading (e.g., in kinematic hardening models), plastic free energy can be partially recovered, causing the accumulated plastic work to decrease without violating thermodynamic principles. Nevertheless, in the current paper, and for the sake of simplification, plastic free energy was not considered, as in a previous work from the authors [49]. The plastic power condition can be easily implemented as a penalty during ANN training to weakly impose the second law of thermodynamics.

2.2.2. Tangent stiffness symmetry

For a general orthotropic material the tangent stiffness \mathbf{C} is a symmetric fourth order tensor with 9 independent components. thus the general mapping between the elastic strain and stress may be expressed in matrix form as [42]:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & & & \\ & C_{22} & C_{23} & & & \\ & & C_{33} & & & \\ & & & C_{44} & & \\ & \text{symm} & & C_{55} & & \\ & & & & C_{66} & \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \epsilon_{zz} \\ 2\epsilon_{yz} \\ 2\epsilon_{xz} \\ 2\epsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

The symmetries of \mathbf{C} ensure the physically correct state of stress is the one that maximizes the plastic dissipation for a given plastic strain rate [3]. Under plastic deformation, a general tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} may be considered as in Eq. (7), which remains symmetric. When strain hardening effects are present, \mathbf{H} is also positive definite, to ensure that the strain energy is positive and weakly convex [32,50]. The latter is also a sufficient condition for the uniqueness of the elastoplastic boundary value problem [32]. The condition also guarantees time-consistent solutions.

In the context of ANN training, the symmetry condition could be applied either as a loss penalty, forcing the equality between the matrix components, or as a hard constraint. For the latter, Jekel et al. [50] proposed a transformation layer, without learnable

parameters, to map a vector input to a symmetric positive definite matrix. The transformation is based on the Cholesky factorization of a real symmetric matrix \mathbf{C} , expressed as:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{L}^T, \tag{13}$$

where \mathbf{L} is a real-valued lower triangular matrix, defined as:

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} L_{11} & & & & & & \\ L_{21} & L_{22} & & & & & \\ L_{31} & L_{32} & L_{33} & & & & \\ & & & L_{44} & & & \\ & & & & L_{55} & & \\ & & & & & L_{66} & \\ & & & & & & \end{bmatrix}, \tag{14}$$

with the diagonal elements kept positive, to force the output matrix to be symmetric positive definite. The positiveness of the diagonal elements can be enforced with a suitable activation function (e.g. ReLU). Xu et al. [32], on the other hand, weakly impose the symmetric positive definiteness of the tangent stiffness by obtaining \mathbf{L} directly through the ANN output.

2.2.3. Stress triaxiality

The stress triaxiality represents the distribution of stress in the three orthotropic axes and is defined as [51]:

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{\sigma_h}{\sigma_{VM}} \quad \text{with} \quad \sigma_h = \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}), \tag{15}$$

where σ_h the hydrostatic stress and σ_{VM} the von Mises equivalent stress. A negative value of triaxiality, indicates a compressive stress state, and a positive value corresponds to a tensile state, while a value close to zero indicates predominantly shear or deviatoric stress conditions (pure shear loading) [52,53]. The ranges of stress triaxiality for each state are a requirement for a constitutive model and are specified as follows: $-\infty \leq \mathcal{T} \leq +\infty$, for a general 3D stress state and $-2/3 \leq \mathcal{T} \leq 2/3$ for a 2D plane stress state.

2.2.4. Lode angle parameter

The Lode angle θ , or the Lode parameter L , relates the third invariant J_3 of the deviatoric stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$ with the von Mises equivalent stress σ_{VM} , such that [51,52]:

$$L = -\cos(3\theta) = -\frac{27}{2} \frac{J_3}{\sigma_{VM}^3} \quad \text{with} \quad J_3 = \theta(\boldsymbol{\sigma}'). \tag{16}$$

The Lode angle θ can be normalized as follows:

$$\bar{\theta} = 1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \arccos\left(\frac{J_3}{\sigma_{VM}^3}\right). \tag{17}$$

The Lode angle range is $0 \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{3}$, while the Lode parameter range is $-1 \leq L \leq 1$.

3. The virtual fields method

3.1. Theoretical development

The Virtual Fields Method (VFM) is a state-of-the-art technique used in the inverse identification of constitutive parameters [54]. A key advantage of the VFM is that it does not resort to the Finite Element Method (FEM), resulting in increased computational efficiency [6]. Moreover, it also avoids having to model the boundary conditions and the specimen's geometry [55,56]. The VFM is based on the Principle of Virtual Work (PVW) represented, in the absence of body forces, by the equilibrium [13,57]:

$$-\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* dV + \int_{\partial V} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{u}^* dS = 0, \tag{18}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*$ is the virtual strain, \mathbf{u}^* is the virtual displacement, V is the volume of the solid, \mathbf{T} is the vector of loading tractions and S is the surface with applied tractions. The virtual displacements are mathematical functions independent of the measured displacements. The equilibrium from Eq. (18) holds for any virtual displacement \mathbf{u}^* as long as it is continuous, piece-wise differentiable over the specimen's body and kinematically admissible, in order to satisfy the displacement boundary conditions. The virtual strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*$ are derived from the virtual displacements \mathbf{u}^* by taking the gradient of the displacements, that is [13]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u}^* + \nabla \mathbf{u}^{*T}). \tag{19}$$

Besides the referred requirements, there are no specific rules for the choice of virtual fields. Nevertheless, it is convenient to find expressions such that the virtual displacement \mathbf{u}^* would be constant along the boundary of prescribed displacements [13,55]. This is

due to the fact that the traction distribution is often unknown and only the resultant force \mathbf{F} is available from the load cell, allowing to simplify the calculation of the external virtual work $\mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^*$, as follows [58]:

$$\mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^* = \mathbf{u}^* \int_{\partial S} \mathbf{T} dS \approx \mathbf{u}^* \cdot \mathbf{F}. \quad (20)$$

Given that full-field measurements are only available at the surface of the specimen, an assumption for the through-thickness behaviour of the material is necessary [56]. Thin specimens are often employed in mechanical testing, as such it is common to assume a plane stress state, resulting modification of Eq. (18), for a specimen with thickness h [55]:

$$-h \int_S \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* dS + h \int_{\partial S} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{u}^* dL = 0, \quad (21)$$

where S and ∂S are, respectively, the surface and the boundary of the specimen. In full-field measurements, the displacements are captured using DIC techniques in a large number of points or subsets, as such, the integral in Eq. (21) can be approximated as a discrete sum for any time stage t . Assuming a suitable set of virtual fields is used, the identification process is carried out by minimizing a loss function with respect to the constitutive parameters χ defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}(\chi, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_t} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{VF}}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{pts}}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^j(\chi, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{*j(i)} \cdot S^j - \mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^* \right)^2, \quad (22)$$

where S^j is the area of the j th element and N_{VF} , N_t , N_{pts} are the number of virtual fields, time stages and measurement points, respectively. Although any kinematically admissible virtual fields could be used, their choice is a key step of the VFM with great impact in the final solution due to several key factors. First, the sensitivity to material behaviour plays a crucial role, as certain virtual fields emphasize specific aspects of the behaviour, such as elasticity or plasticity, more effectively. Virtual fields aligned with the dominant material behaviour can enhance the solution accuracy. Second, each virtual field determines how various regions of the measured strain and stress fields contribute to the equilibrium equations. This also affects the distribution of noise and measurement errors in the final solution. Third, the numerical stability of the solution depends on the mathematical properties of the virtual fields, such as their continuity, differentiability, and orthogonality. Fourth, the completeness and independence of the chosen set of virtual fields are vital to capture all independent modes of deformation relevant to the material behaviour. An incomplete set may leave certain material parameters under-determined, leading to inaccurate results. Lastly, the virtual fields can be defined to have specific physical interpretations, such as representing pure bending or shear modes relevant to the loading conditions.

The virtual fields are often user-defined, nonetheless, systematic procedures are available to automatically define them, namely: the stiffness-based and the sensitivity-based virtual fields [55]. It is important to refer that the User-Defined Virtual Fields (UDVFs) are tied to the user's own expertise and intuition and do not evolve in time.

3.2. Coupled RNN-VFM indirect training

In the current work, the authors revisit the indirect training methodology presented in a previous paper [1]. The method consists on coupling the VFM to indirectly train a GRU-based RNN model (Fig. 1) in order to learn the unified elastoplastic response a material. During training, the strains, obtained from the spatial gradient of the measured displacements, are fed as inputs to the RNN material model \mathcal{M} which predicts the stress components. Then, the equilibrium can be evaluated globally by means of the PVW. The network's parameters are searched until the gap between the internal and the external components of the virtual work is minimized.

Fig. 1. Coupled RNN-VFM indirect training method for implicit constitutive modelling, using user-defined virtual fields [1]. The entities \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{b} are the parameters and the biases of the RNN material model \mathcal{M} , respectively.

4. GRU-based RNNs

In the current paper, RNNs based on Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) are employed [59]. A basic GRU cell is composed of the following key components: an update gate, a reset gate, a new gate and the final state (see Fig. 2(a)). The update gate (z_t) determines how much of the previous hidden state is to be retained and how much it should be updated with new information and is defined by the mapping:

$$z_t = \text{sig} (\mathbf{W}_{xz} \mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xz} + \mathbf{W}_{hz} \mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hz}). \quad (23)$$

Analogously, the reset gate (r_t) is defined such that:

$$r_t = \text{sig} (\mathbf{W}_{xr} \mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xr} + \mathbf{W}_{hr} \mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hr}), \quad (24)$$

and specifies which information from the previous hidden state should be forgotten. The new gate (n_t) computes a new candidate hidden state based on the input and previous hidden state, such that:

$$n_t = \tanh (\mathbf{W}_{xn} \mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xn} + r_t \odot [\mathbf{W}_{hn} \mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hn}]). \quad (25)$$

Finally, the final state (\mathbf{h}_t) combines the previous hidden state and the new memory content, controlled by the update gate, through the following:

$$\mathbf{h}_t = (1 - z_t) \odot \mathbf{h}_{t-1} + z_t \odot n_t. \quad (26)$$

The variables \mathbf{h}_t and \mathbf{x}_t are, respectively, the hidden state and the input at time t , while $\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}$ is the hidden state at time $t - 1$, or the initial hidden state at $t = 0$. The entities sig and tanh are, respectively, the sigmoid and the hyperbolic tangent activation functions and the operator \odot is the element-wise product. The weight matrices \mathbf{W} and bias vectors \mathbf{b} are appended with double indices identifying the mapping between the different components of the GRU cell. A deeper description of these mathematical entities and their corresponding dimensions, in the context of the present work, is provided in Table 1 [1]. The hidden state \mathbf{h} is the key element behind the flow of information relating previous time steps and future predictions. In a way analogous to the internal variables of classical constitutive laws, \mathbf{h} carries the information about the current plastic state of the material [1,27].

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of (a) a standard GRU cell and (b) an unrolled recurrent neural network.

Table 1

Mathematical entities, and corresponding dimensions for a GRU-based RNN where n is the batch size, k the sequence length, n_{cells} the number of GRU cells, s_{in} the input size, s_{out} the output size and s_{hid} the hidden size.

Component	Entity	Dimensions	Description
Input	\mathbf{x}_t	$(n \times k \times s_{\text{in}})$	Strain sequences
Previous state	\mathbf{h}_{t-1}	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time $t - 1$
Final state	\mathbf{h}_t	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time t
Output	$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_t$	$(n \times s_{\text{out}})$	Stress tensor at time t
Update gate	$\mathbf{W}_{x(z r)n}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{in}})$	Input-to-hidden weights of 1st GRU cell
Reset gate or New gate	$\mathbf{b}_{x(z r)n}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Input-to-hidden bias
	$\mathbf{W}_{h(z r)n}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden-to-hidden weights
	$\mathbf{b}_{h(z r)n}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden-to-hidden bias

5. Materials and methods

5.1. RNN architecture

The RNN architecture chosen for this work is depicted in Fig. 3 and an overview of the corresponding constituent modules is provided in Table 2. The input consists of strain sequences with length $k = 4$, which are first processed by two GRU cells. The

information is then forwarded through the three fully-connected (FC) layers. The network predicts the material tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} by the inclusion of a SPD layer, as proposed by Jekel et al. [50] (see Section 2.2.2), albeit adapted here to an isotropic material under plane stress. A dropout layer features between the GRU modules with a probability $p = 0.1$, i.e. at each iteration 10% of the connections are randomly deactivated in order to prevent overfitting by discouraging individual neurons from relying too much on other specific neurons [60]. Residual connections are added to the outputs of layers FC2 and FC3, allowing the temporal information encoded by the GRU modules to be “remembered” at those points on the forward pass. These connections greatly improve the gradient flow during backpropagation and help stabilize the training process [61]. The residuals are scaled by a learnable parameter θ_i to prevent them from overwhelming the outputs of the FC layers. The residuals with unmatching dimensions are passed through a linear layer in order to ensure dimensional compatibility during the addition. The sigmoid-weighted linear unit (SiLU), a smooth approximation of the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), was chosen as activation function. For more details on the SiLU, the reader is invited to refer to Fig. A.23 from Appendix A.

Fig. 3. GRU-based RNN architecture for material modelling. Sequences of length $k = 4$ of the scaled strain tensor $\epsilon' = [\epsilon'_{xx} \ \epsilon'_{yy} \ \epsilon'_{xy}]$ are mapped to the material tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} due to the inclusion of a SPD layer. The green blocks depict linear fully-connected (FC) layers. Residual connections are drawn with solid black lines, while the dash dotted pattern depicts residuals transformed to ensure dimensional compatibility. Residual connections are weighted by a learnable parameter θ_i . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2

Overview of the constituent models of the GRU-based architecture adopted in this work, and corresponding number of hidden units and trainable parameters.

Module	Hidden units	Trainable parameters
GRU	2	9888
FC1	32	1056
FC2	32	1056
FC3	6	198
Residual 1	N/A	1
Residual 2	6	193
SPD	6	N/A

5.2. Training database

Here, synthetic data was used to simulate experimental DIC data in order to have a reference in the overall process. Therefore, the training dataset was built from multiple virtual experiments of a heterogeneous biaxial test. For a general cruciform specimen under biaxial loading, like the one depicted in Fig. 4(a), the region of interest (ROI) corresponds to one fourth of the central zone. Hence, symmetry boundary conditions are defined at the left ($x = 0$) and bottom ($y = 0$) edges and displacements prescribed at each arm of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 4(c). The virtual experiments were generated with displacements of different magnitudes (in mm), being prescribed in pairs (u_x, u_y) , as detailed in Table 3.

Table 3

Paired combinations of displacements (u_x, u_y) prescribed to the arms of the cruciform specimen.

		u_y					
		0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
u_x	0.5	(0.5,0.5)	(0.5,1.0)	(0.5,1.5)	(0.5,2.0)	(0.5,2.5)	(0.5,3.0)
	1.0	(1.0,0.5)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.5)	(1.0,2.0)	(1.0,2.5)	(1.0,3.0)
	1.5	(1.5,0.5)	(1.5,1.0)	(1.5,1.5)	(1.5,2.0)	(1.5,2.5)	(1.5,3.0)
	2.0	(2.0,0.5)	(2.0,1.0)	(2.0,1.5)	(2.0,2.0)	(2.0,2.5)	(2.0,3.0)
	2.5	(2.5,0.5)	(2.5,1.0)	(2.5,1.5)	(2.5,2.0)	(2.5,2.5)	(2.5,3.0)
	3.0	(3.0,0.5)	(3.0,1.0)	(3.0,1.5)	(3.0,2.0)	(3.0,2.5)	(3.0,3.0)

The virtual experiments were carried out with Abaqus Standard software [62], assuming plane stress and small strains. The material behaviour was considered isotropic, with the flow stress evolving according to the Swift's law:

$$\sigma_Y = K (\epsilon_0 + \bar{\epsilon}^p)^n \quad \text{with} \quad \epsilon_0 = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{K}\right)^{1/n}, \quad (27)$$

where σ_Y is the flow stress, $\bar{\epsilon}^p$ the equivalent plastic strain, σ_0 the initial yield stress, K and n are material-specific hardening parameters. The constitutive parameters are listed in Table 4.

The geometry was discretized using CPS4R elements with an average size of 0.52 mm, resulting in a total of 2121 elements. Similar refinement levels have been cited in the literature for this specimen ([58,63], among others). Reduced integration elements were chosen to simulate DIC subsets from full-field measurements, thus, the field output variables were extracted at the centroids of the elements. For each time stage, strain and stress tensors were extracted at all the measurement points and the force applied at specimen's arms was computed from the equilibrium of the internal forces through the following:

$$Fl = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i A_i h, \quad (28)$$

where F is the global force, l the length of the specimen, n is the number of elements, A is the area of the element and h the thickness.

Table 4
Constitutive parameters for the soft steel material.

E [GPa]	ν	σ_0 [MPa]	K [MPa]	n
210	0.33	160	565	0.26

The whole dataset contained a total of 36 virtual experiments. The data was shuffled and split in half, such that one part was used for training and the remaining part for validation. The training set was then split such that 70% of the virtual experiments were used for training and the remaining 30% for testing. The full training domain is shown on the scatter plot from Fig. 5. Prior to training, the input data was scaled to have zero mean and unit variance, as follows:

$$\epsilon' = \frac{\epsilon - \mu}{s}, \quad (29)$$

where ϵ' is the scaled strain tensor, $\mu = [\mu_{\epsilon_{xx}} \ \mu_{\epsilon_{yy}} \ \mu_{\epsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of mean values and $s = [s_{\epsilon_{xx}} \ s_{\epsilon_{yy}} \ s_{\epsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of variances of the strain tensor components, respectively. The statistical variables μ and s were saved for later usage. For each virtual experiment, the inputs have dimensions $[n_{pts} \times n_t \times k \times 3]$, where n_{pts} is the number of measurement points, i.e. the number of elements, n_t is the number of time stages, k the sequence length and the last dimension the number of strain components.

Fig. 4. Biaxial test virtual experiment: (a) selected region of interest, (b) specimen's geometry and (c) applied boundary conditions.

Fig. 5. Principal strain and normalized yield locus diagrams for the complete set of virtual experiments used for training, taken from the material points at all the time stages. The grey colour highlights material points in the elastic regime.

5.3. Training procedure

The RNN model was developed using PyTorch library, following the indirect training methodology described in Section 3.2 without labelled data. The user-defined virtual fields considered for training are mathematically defined in Table 5. For each virtual field, the variables W and H are the width and height of the specimen, respectively, while X and Y are the material coordinates in the reference frame. The resulting virtual displacement and virtual strain contour maps are shown, respectively, in Fig. B.24, Fig. B.25 and Fig. B.26 from Appendix B. The best combination of virtual fields was determined by a sensitivity analysis.

Training was performed with the Adam optimizer with weight decay factor 10^{-3} . A linear warm-up scheduler was configured to increase the learning rate from an initial value of 10^{-5} up to a maximum learning rate η_{\max} within the first 10 epochs, followed by a gradual decay according to a cosine annealing scheduler, defined as [64,65]:

$$\eta_t = \eta_{\min} + \frac{1}{2} (\eta_{\max} - \eta_{\min}) \left(1 + \cos \left(\frac{T_{\text{cur}}}{T_{\text{max}}} \pi \right) \right), \quad (30)$$

where η_t is the current learning rate, η_{\min} is the minimum learning rate, T_{cur} and T_{max} are the current iteration and the maximum number of iterations, respectively. The minimum learning rate η_{\min} was set to 10^{-5} . For each epoch, the order of the virtual experiments was shuffled, as well as the corresponding inputs along the time dimension. Mini-batch training was employed due to GPU memory restrictions. Therefore, considering that each experiment has a variable number of time stages, the batch size $N_{t,b}$ was defined taking the floor division of the total number of time stages N_t by an integer $d_{\text{batch}} \in \{2, 4, 8, 16, 32\}$. An early-stopping criterion was implemented to prevent overfitting and interrupt the training if the test loss did not improve after 350 epochs. In RNNs, gradients can grow exponentially during backpropagation through layers, or time steps, becoming excessively large (exploding gradients). This leads to unstable training dynamics that can make the network fail to learn effectively, as weight updates become too large to converge to a stable solution [66]. To prevent the gradients from exploding, clipping was employed, based on the L2 norm of the gradients, through a clipping parameter c_{norm} .

The loss function was based on the VFM loss from Eq. (22), adapted to mini-batch training, such that:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta, \epsilon) = \frac{1}{N_{t,b} \cdot N_{\text{VF}}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{VF}}} \left(\mathbf{w}_{\text{int},k}^{*(i)} - \mathbf{w}_{\text{ext},k}^{*(i)} \right)^2, \quad (31)$$

where $N_{t,b}$ is the number of time stages per batch. The physics-based constraints used in this work were the plastic power condition, the stress triaxiality and the lode parameter, added as penalty terms to the VFM loss, resulting in a multi-objective loss with the general form:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta, \epsilon) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i \mathcal{L}_i, \quad (32)$$

where the constants λ_i are scaling factors used to balance the loss terms, \mathcal{L}_i is the i th objective loss to minimize and k is the total number of conflicting objectives. The implementation for each penalty is presented in Table 6. The inequalities were imposed through the ReLU6 function, which is a modified version of the ReLU, where the activation is limited to a maximum size of 6 [67]. The preference was due to improved training stability. The loss balancing terms λ_i were automatically computed during training, based on the Relative Loss Balancing with Random Lookback (ReLoBRaLo) algorithm, introduced by Bischof and Kraus (2021) [68]. The algorithm adapts the terms λ_i based on a moving average and a random lookback mechanism, at each iteration, as follows:

$$\lambda_i^j = \alpha \left(\beta \lambda_i^{j-1} + (1 - \beta) \hat{\lambda}_i^{j:0} \right) + (1 - \alpha) \hat{\lambda}_i^{j:j-1}, \quad (33)$$

where λ_i^j is the scaling for the i th loss term at iteration j , α is the moving average parameter and β a Bernoulli random variable with a value close to 1. The term $\hat{\lambda}_i^{j:j'}$ is responsible for computing the scalings based on the relative improvements of each loss between iterations j and j' , such that:

$$\hat{\lambda}_i^{j:j'} = k \cdot \frac{\exp \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_i^j}{\tau \mathcal{L}_i^{j'} + \epsilon} - \max \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_i^j}{\mathcal{L}_i^{j'}} \right) \right)}{\sum_{m=1}^k \exp \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_m^j}{\tau \mathcal{L}_m^{j'} + \epsilon} - \max \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_m^j}{\mathcal{L}_m^{j'}} \right) \right)}, \quad (34)$$

with k being the total number of loss terms, \mathcal{L}_i^j and $\mathcal{L}_i^{j'}$ the values of the i th loss term at iterations j and j' , respectively; τ is a hyperparameter that controls the amplitude of the scalings and ϵ a small number. The parameter α controls the weight given to past scalings in relation to the scalings from the current iteration, while β allows the model to occasionally look back until the start of training.

A hyperparameter tuning was performed in order to select the best combination of parameters α , β , τ , along with the maximum learning rate η_{\max} , the mini-batch size and the gradient norm clipping value c_{norm} .

During training, additional metrics were logged to provide a better insight into the training dynamics. Namely, the predictive accuracy was monitored through the error between the predicted stress $\hat{\sigma}$ and reference stress σ , such that:

$$\mathcal{L}_\sigma = \frac{1}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} (\hat{\sigma} - \sigma)^2, \quad (35)$$

along with the error of the resulting approximation of the global force, given as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{F}} = \frac{1}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \left(\hat{\mathbf{F}} - \mathbf{F} \right)^2, \quad (36)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{F}}$ is the global force obtained by taking the integration of the stress, as in Eq. (28). It is important to note that these metrics were logged solely for information purposes, during the test loop, and were not used for training.

Table 5
Full set of possible user-defined virtual fields considered for training.

Virtual field	u_x^*	u_y^*
$\mathbf{u}^{*(1)}$	$\frac{X}{W}$	0
$\mathbf{u}^{*(2)}$	0	$\frac{Y}{H}$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(3)}$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(4)}$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\cos\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$	$\cos\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(5)}$	$\frac{X}{W}$	$\cos\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\cos\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(6)}$	$\cos\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)\cos\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$	$\frac{Y}{H}$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(7)}$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sqrt[3]{\frac{Y}{H}}$	$\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)\sqrt[3]{\frac{X}{W}}$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(8)}$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)$	0
$\mathbf{u}^{*(9)}$	0	$\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(10)}$	$\sin\left(8.5 \cdot \frac{X}{W}\pi\right)$	0
$\mathbf{u}^{*(11)}$	0	$\sin\left(8.5 \cdot \frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(12)}$	$\sin\left(8.5 \cdot \frac{X}{W}\pi\right)$	$\sin\left(8.5 \cdot \frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(13)}$	$\sin\left(3 \cdot \frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\cos\left(3 \cdot \frac{Y}{H}\pi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)$	0
$\mathbf{u}^{*(14)}$	0	$\sin\left(3 \cdot \frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)\cos\left(3 \cdot \frac{X}{W}\pi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)$

Table 6
Penalty terms used for training, with k being the k th sample and N_b the total samples per batch.

	Penalty term
Plastic power	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Wp}} = \frac{\lambda_2}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \text{ReLU6}\left(-\sigma_{(k)} : \epsilon_{(k)}^p\right)^2$
Lode parameter	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Lode}} = \frac{\lambda_3}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \text{ReLU6}\left(- L_{(k)} + 1\right)^2$
Stress triaxiality	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Triax}} = \frac{\lambda_4}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \text{ReLU6}\left(- \tau_{(k)} + \frac{2}{3}\right)^2$

5.4. Validation database

From the data generation phase, 18 virtual experiments based on the cruciform specimen were kept separate for the validation set. This set of experiments had different prescribed displacements than the ones used for training. From this set, a virtual experiment with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm was chosen for further analysis.

Three additional heterogeneous mechanical specimens, documented in the literature for constitutive model calibration, have also been considered for validation purposes, each of which exhibiting increasing levels of geometric complexity within the respective regions of interest (ROI): the S specimen [69], the Sigma specimen [70] and the D specimen [71]. An uniaxial external load along the y -direction is normally applied to each specimen. The complex shapes induce multiaxial heterogeneous stress states, despite the loading being uniaxial. For the purpose of the present work, a displacement u_y is prescribed at the top-surface of each specimen with magnitude 2.0 mm for the D specimen and 1.5 mm for the S and Sigma specimens. The corresponding geometries, principal strain distributions, yield locus and equivalent plastic strain field, when using a classical constitutive model, are illustrated in detail in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively.

Fig. 6. Geometric definition of the three heterogeneous mechanical specimens chosen for model validation: (a) S specimen, (b) Sigma specimen and (c) D specimen.

Fig. 7. Major and minor strain distributions, normalized yield locus and equivalent plastic strain at the last time stage for (a) the cruciform specimen with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, (b) the S specimen (c) the Sigma specimen and (d) the D specimen. The grey colour highlights material points in the elastic regime. These values were retrieved using the von Mises model with isotropic hardening.

5.5. Validation procedure

5.5.1. Error statistics

Model performance was evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE), a standard benchmark metric in ML to assess the accuracy of predictive models. A lower RMSE indicates higher accuracy. RMSE quantifies the average magnitude of errors between the predicted and observed values as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{\sigma} - \sigma)^2}, \quad (37)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}$ is the predicted stress, σ the actual stress and N the number of observations. Additionally, the absolute error, i.e.:

$$\delta = |\hat{\sigma} - \sigma| \quad (38)$$

was used to compare the predicted stress fields and stress–strain curves with the reference FEA solution.

5.5.2. Validation KPI

The reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR), introduced by Peshave et al. [72], was also used to check the physical correctness of the RNN’s predictions. The RAFR exploits the fact that, in uniaxial tensile tests, the load applied by the testing machine F_a is known. Moreover, the horizontal average of the stress multiplied by the cross-sectional area F_c^i should be equal to the applied load at any cross-section (see Fig. 8). For a given cross-section i , the reconstructed force F_c^i is computed by integrating the axial stress σ_{yy} , as follows:

$$F_c^i = \int_{S_c} \sigma_{yy} dS_c, \quad (39)$$

where S_c is the surface of that particular cross-section of the mechanical specimen. Assuming constant stress through the thickness, the surface integral reduces to:

$$F_c^i = h \int_{l_i} \sigma_{yy} dl_i, \quad (40)$$

where h is the specimen’s thickness. Considering a regular grid of measurement points with sufficiently high spatial density, the line integral can be approximated as:

$$F_c^i = h S_i \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} \sigma_{yy}^j, \quad (41)$$

where N_i is the number of evaluation points at the cross-section i and S_i is the step size. The RAFR is then computed as:

$$\text{RAFR} = \frac{F_c^i}{F_a}. \quad (42)$$

The metric is used to evaluate how well the section-averaged stress field matches the applied force at each cross-section. Any deviation from the ideal value of 1 indicates problems with the approximation of the stress field.

Fig. 8. Schematic of RAFR calculation. The force acting at the i -th cross-section is reconstructed by integrating the corresponding axial stress σ_{yy}^i along the cross-section length l_i and multiplying it by the thickness h .

5.5.3. UMAT implementation

Another step taken to validate the trained RNN models involved incorporating them as material constitutive models in a FEA solver (here, Abaqus Standard) through a custom user material subroutine (UMAT). The code was developed in C++ and made use of the official C++ implementation of PyTorch (LibTorch). The architecture and data flow for the UMAT implementation are described in the flowchart of Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Flowchart of the UMAT-RNN implementation.

6. Results

6.1. Hyperparameter tuning

Hyperparameter tuning was performed to select the optimal parameters α , β , τ of the ReLoBRaLo algorithm, alongside with the maximum learning rate η_{\max} , the gradient norm clipping value c_{norm} and the batch size through the integer parameter d_{batch} . The base network architecture was the one shown in Fig. 3. The hyperparameter sweep functionality of platform Weights & Biases was used to manage the tuning process, monitor and log the results. The tuning relied on the Bayesian method combined with the hyperband algorithm to terminate underperforming runs. The Bayesian method uses a probabilistic model to choose the best parameter configurations to test, aiming to minimize a target metric [73]. The hyperband stopping algorithm evaluates if a run should stop or continue, at one or more predefined iterations, called brackets. When a run reaches a bracket, its objective metric is compared with all previously reported values. The run is terminated if the metric is too high. For the hyperparameter tuning of this work, each model was run using a subset composed of the virtual fields 1 through 9, during 150 epochs, and the mean squared error of the predicted stress \mathcal{L}_σ , as well as the corresponding approximation of the global force \mathcal{L}_F were logged during the test loop. Note that these metrics were not used for training, only for information purposes. The Bayes method was set to minimize \mathcal{L}_σ as an objective.

The universe of parameter values given to the program to be cycled through is shown in Table 7. The searching domain resulted in a total of 2160 runs to be launched with a unique hyperparameter combination. However, due to time constraints, the sweep agent was configured to launch a maximum number of 150 runs, 113 of which ended up being terminated by the hyperband algorithm. The resulting metric \mathcal{L}_σ for the remaining 37 runs is presented in the scatter plot of Fig. 10. The learning curves for the 5 models highlighted by the black solid line can be closely inspected in Fig. 11 and the corresponding training stats are compiled in Table 8. The models are identified by the letters A to E, respecting their order of appearance and colour code in the scatter plot. The corresponding sets of hyperparameters are also shown in Table 7, with the best combination found on the tuning session marked in boldface.

Table 7

Searching domain for the hyperparameter tuning and hyperparameters for the five highlighted models. The best combination of hyperparameters is marked in boldface.

Parameter	Searching domain	A	B	C	D	E
α	{0.9, 0.99, 0.999}	0.99	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999
β	{0.9, 0.99, 0.999}	0.99	0.9	0.999	0.99	0.999
τ	{10, 1, 0.001, 0.0001}	0.001	0.001	10	0.001	1
η_{\max}	{0.01, 0.005, 0.001}	0.01	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
c_{norm}	{1, 2, 5, 10}	1	5	5	5	10
d_{batch}	{2, 4, 8, 16, 32}	32	4	8	8	16

Results show that the best run corresponds to model E with a metric \mathcal{L}_σ as low as 206.462 MPa². Additionally, the learning curves show that model E not only exhibit the most stable training dynamics, but also achieved the lowest VFM training loss. Worthy of

Fig. 10. Resulting \mathcal{L}_σ metric for the non-interrupted runs, the line marks the runs with lower metric.

Fig. 11. Learning curves of the five models selected from the hyperparameter tuning: (a) VFM train loss, (b) VFM test loss, (c) loss of the stress prediction and (d) loss of the approximation of the global force.

Table 8
Training stats for the five models under analysis.

	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VFM}}^{\text{train}}$ [J ²]	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VFM}}^{\text{test}}$ [J ²]	\mathcal{L}_σ [MPa ²]	\mathcal{L}_F [N ²]
Model A	2743.325	2255.196	2239.393	3139.855
Model B	22010.424	22695.210	436.148	39152.723
Model C	5291.868	5490.525	338.928	9150.831
Model D	6419.348	4824.316	291.314	8017.327
Model E	2098.595	2340.699	206.462	2734.911

note is the fact that Model A achieved similar values for the VFM loss, for both training and testing, however the stress error was one order of magnitude higher. In contrast, the remaining models show higher VFM losses but lower stress error. These observations allow to conclude that the hyperparameter combination corresponding to model E is the best, not only achieving the lowest error but also allowing the stress error and the force approximation to correlate well with the minimization of the VFM losses. All the following analyses were performed using the hyperparameter combination selected here as the best.

6.2. Sensitivity analysis to the virtual fields

6.2.1. Discretization error

When calculating the equilibrium based on the PVW, theoretically, each virtual field should yield an exact balance between the external and virtual works. Nonetheless, some discrepancies may occur due to, e.g., mesh discretization or background noise. The virtual fields shown in Table 5 were mathematically defined to ensure compatibility with the boundary conditions. The kinematic admissibility can be confirmed upon inspecting the corresponding contour maps shown in Figs. B.24 and B.25 from Appendix B, where it can be seen that every virtual field is zero at the edges with symmetry boundary conditions and either zero or constant at the edges with applied tractions. However, it is critical to know the underlying error related to mesh discretization, which is independent of the constitutive model.

In Fig. 12 the curves for the internal and external virtual works, corresponding to each virtual field, are shown. The data was obtained for the virtual experiment based on the cruciform specimen, with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, and calculated based on the reference field outputs extracted from Abaqus software. The curves show, in general, a good match between the internal and external virtual work for virtual fields that activate the components of the global force, although slight deviations emerge towards later time stages, particularly for the virtual fields 10, 11 and 12. For the virtual fields that do not activate the external work (i.e. 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 13 and 14), the internal virtual work starts to increasingly deviates from the external work curve over time, to an extent that depends on the virtual field.

Given that the kinematic admissibility is ensured and these are results obtained from virtual experiments without experimental noise, these discrepancies are likely due to mesh discretization. The use of reduced integration elements to simulate DIC subsets may have led to a mesh that is too coarse to capture local variations in strain or stress within certain regions of the specimen, causing imbalances in the virtual work calculations.

Fig. 12. Internal and external virtual work, for the whole set of virtual fields, along the time stages of the virtual experiment based on the cruciform specimen with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm.

6.2.2. Number of virtual fields

In theory, the higher the number of virtual fields the more accurate should be the stress reconstruction through the VFM. However, certain combinations of virtual fields may introduce undesirable effects when coupling the VFM with neural network training. Moreover, due to computational constraints and the manual method of introducing the virtual fields, their selection must be made correctly. As such, an analysis was conducted in order to determine the effects of the choice of virtual fields on both the training dynamics and predictive accuracy of the RNN model. For the purpose, various models were fully trained using the optimal combination of hyperparameters identified from the hyperparameter tuning (i.e. Model E - see Section 6.1) and different subsets of virtual fields. The model using the virtual fields 1 through 9 was taken as baseline. Each model was given a name and its correspondence with a given subset of virtual fields, as well as the resulting RMSE on the validation set after training, are shown in Table 9.

Table 9

Model naming and subsets of virtual fields used for training. RMSE metrics on the validation set with virtual experiments based on the cruciform specimen. The baseline model is shown in boldface, and enclosed in parentheses is the percentage gain or loss in the RMSE relative to the baseline.

Model	Virtual fields	RMSE validation [MPa]			
		Min.	Mean	Median	Max.
4VF	{1-4}	24.881 (+87.8%)	32.804 (+84.4%)	32.361 (+101.1%)	41.399 (+65.6%)
6VF	{1-6}	23.766 (+79.4%)	30.288 (+70.3%)	29.586 (+83.8%)	36.894 (+47.6%)
7VF	{1-7}	15.791 (+19.2%)	18.691 (+5%)	18.217 (+13.2%)	22.294 (-10.7%)
9VF	{1-9}	13.242	17.785	16.089	24.993
10VF	{1-9,12}	12.903 (-2.62%)	13.955 (-21.5%)	13.711 (-14.7%)	15.333 (-38.65%)
11VF _a	{1-11}	12.892 (-2.64%)	13.979 (-21.4%)	13.842 (-13.9%)	15.325 (-38.68)
11VF _b	{1-9,13,14}	10.747 (-18.8%)	11.778 (-33.7%)	11.604 (-27.8%)	13.076 (-47.68%)
12VF	{1-9,12,13,14}	10.537 (-20.4%)	11.810 (-33.5%)	11.498 (-28.5%)	13.644 (-45.4%)

Analysing the results from Table 9, the RMSE metrics clearly show that the number of virtual fields has a significant impact on the predictive accuracy of the RNN. It is seen that any given model trained with larger sets of virtual fields than the baseline, shows substantial improvements. Models 11VF_b and 12VF both achieve similar RMSE and the highest percent error reduction. Models 10VF and 11VF_a have similar RMSE, confirming that there is no substantial difference when opting between the pair of virtual fields 10,11 or the virtual field 12. The latter is component-wise identical to the former, however it has both components of the external force simultaneously active. Regarding the models trained with smaller sets of virtual fields, the 7VF registers an RMSE closer to the baseline and shows significant improvements upon 4VF and 6VF, solely due to the inclusion of virtual field number 7. It is also noticeable that not only the number but also the type of virtual fields influence the final predictive accuracy. Observing the results in more detail and keeping in mind the formulations of Table 5, it can be seen that introducing virtual fields that do not activate the external component of the virtual work (i.e. 7, 13, 14), seems to result in significant improvements, as seen by the relative differences in RMSE obtained by the 7VF model, compared to the baseline, and the 11VF_b compared to the 11VF_a model. In the latter models, the positive effect was due to the introduction of virtual fields 13 and 14, while removing the virtual fields 10 and 11 (which activate the external component of the load).

Extending the analysis on these error metrics to different heterogeneous mechanical specimens, the box plots from Fig. 13 show the component-wise RMSE of the stress tensor obtained with each model. The plots further highlight the general downward trend of error with increasingly larger sets of virtual fields. The error dispersion as well as the magnitude of the outliers is also significantly lower for larger sets.

Looking in detail into each mechanical specimen, the cruciform test shows similar error tendencies for both stresses in the x - and y -directions, with higher errors being registered for the shear component. Here, the RMSE is seen registering large dispersion and outliers for smaller sets of virtual fields, which could be due to the fact that the strain space provided by the cruciform specimen is not very rich in shear states. However, the issue seems to be mitigated with larger sets of virtual fields. Regarding the D specimen, it is interesting to verify that the median errors are, in general, lower than those seen for the cruciform specimen. Given that the strain space provided by the D specimen contains states that fall outside the training domain, this shows that the models were capable of retaining good extrapolation capacity. The S specimen shows similar error metrics to the cruciform except for the stress coincident with the loading direction, exhibiting higher error dispersion and outliers using smaller sets of virtual fields. For the Sigma specimen, overall low median errors are registered, however there seems to be no significant influence coming from the number of virtual fields.

Regarding training dynamics, for the sake of visual clarity, four most distinctive models were selected from Table 9 to be analysed, namely: 9VF (baseline), 4F, 7VF and 12VF. The corresponding learning curves and evolution of the physics-based constraints logged during training are shown in Figs. 14 and 15, respectively. Focusing on the train and test losses (Figs. 14(a) and 14(b)), the curves show a healthy “L” shape exhibiting a sharp decrease at the starting epochs that smoothly evolves into a more gradual slope. This is an indicator of good training stability considering that the training progressed without labelled data and the VFM loss had to be adapted to the context of ANN training. None of the curves seem to achieve total convergence because all of them still show signs of downward trend at the triggering points of early-stopping. The training lasted longer for the baseline model, 9VF, lasting 2661 epochs and allowing it to achieve the lowest value of loss, 202.034 J², followed by 7VF (263.552 J²), 4VF (359.820 J²) and 12VF (898.356 J²). There seems to be no significant overfitting, except for the 4F and 12VF models, with the latter showing a large increase on the test error, causing the early-stopping to trigger at an earlier point in training, at epoch 897. Interestingly,

the 7VF model stopped relatively close to that point, epoch 1194, however resulting in a much lower loss. Looking at the MSE of approximation of the global force (Fig. 14(d)), there seems to be a tight correlation with the test loss given the similarities in both magnitude and behaviour. Analysing the MSE for the predicted stresses (Fig. 14(c)), the curves follow a very different dynamic, decreasing sharply at the starting epochs with a slight undershoot and evolving into what could be considered a plateau. The curves show that, the predictive error improves with larger subsets of virtual fields with the best performer being the 12VF model with an MSE as low as 105.048 MPa² at the early-stopping point, followed, in descending order, by the 9VF (277.658 MPa²), 7VF (303.585 MPa²) and 4VF (1012.424 MPa²).

Concerning the curves of the physics-based constraints, for the plastic power (Fig. 15(a)) all the models register similar dynamic with a sharp increasing at the starting epochs with a slight overshoot smoothly evolving into a plateau, albeit at different magnitudes for each model. The lowest value corresponds to the 4VF model, while the remaining models stabilize into nearly identical values. The lode parameter curves (Fig. 15(b)) register the inverse dynamic, however all the models seem to stabilize at nearly the same values.

Fig. 13. Component-wise RMSE of the stress tensor for the models trained with different subsets of virtual fields corresponding to the virtual experiments based on (a) the cruciform specimen with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, (b) the D specimen, (c) the S specimen and (d) the Sigma specimen.

Fig. 14. Learning curves for four models trained with different subsets of virtual fields: (a) VFM train loss, (b) VFM test loss, (c) MSE for the stress prediction and (d) MSE of the corresponding approximation of the global force.

Fig. 15. Loss curves the physics-based penalty terms for three models trained with different subsets of virtual fields: (a) plastic power, (b) lode parameter and (c) triaxiality factor.

6.3. Effect of loss normalization in the force reconstruction

In this section, the models' predictive accuracy is further assessed by evaluating the quality of the force reconstruction through the RAFR KPI. In a first stage, the analysis is focused on the results obtained by the four models selected in the previous section.

The corresponding RAFR plots obtained for the three heterogeneous uniaxial tests are shown in Fig. 16. In general, the results show that larger sets of virtual fields provide a more accurate force reconstruction. For both the D and S specimens, the 4VF model shows significant scatter along the time stages while the remaining models present smoother curves, well within the error margin of $\pm 10\%$, only with slight deviations in specific areas. However, all the models struggle to obtain an accurate force reconstruction for the Sigma specimen, exhibiting significant scatter across the entire length of the specimen. Nevertheless, the deviations are of lower magnitude for models trained with larger sets of virtual fields. In general, all the models fail to achieve an accurate force reconstruction at the initial time stages for all the specimens. This is due to the fact that the magnitude of the internal virtual work evolves with the time stages. Naturally, in an experiment the earlier a time stage the lower the corresponding internal virtual work, due to lower stresses, and vice-versa. For that reason, it is common to normalize the VFM loss, forcing the different loss terms to lie within similar range, thus avoiding some terms having more importance than others. In the VFM, the loss function from Eq. (22) can be normalized, such that:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{N_{t,b} \cdot N_{VF}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{VF}} \frac{(\mathbf{W}_{\text{int},k}^{*(i)} - \mathbf{W}_{\text{ext},k}^{*(i)})^2}{\max_k \mathbf{W}_{\text{int},k}^{*(i)}}, \quad (43)$$

where the denominator is a vector containing the maximum values of the virtual work for each virtual field. To evaluate the effect of this modification, the four previously selected models were re-trained using the modified loss from the equation above. The corresponding RMSE metrics on the validation set and RAFR plots are shown in Table 10 and Fig. 17, respectively.

Table 10

RMSE metrics on the validation set with the virtual experiments based on the cruciform specimen, obtained by the selected models re-trained with the normalized version of the VFM loss. Enclosed in parentheses are the percentage gain or loss in RMSE, relative to the homologous with the denormalized loss.

Model	RMSE validation [MPa]			
	Min.	Mean	Median	Max.
LN-4VF	27.506 (+10.5%)	37.072 (+13.0%)	36.664 (+13.2%)	47.575 (+14.9%)
LN-7VF	12.275 (-22.2%)	15.675 (-16.1%)	14.696 (-19.3%)	19.913 (-10.6%)
LN-9VF	10.449 (-21.0%)	14.236 (-19.9%)	14.065 (-12.5%)	18.935 (-24.2%)
LN-12VF	8.649 (-17.9%)	10.273 (-13.0%)	9.804 (-15.1%)	12.583 (-7.7%)

Analysing the results from Table 10, it is clear that normalizing the VFM loss has a positive impact on the final predictive accuracy, with all the models showing substantial error reductions across the board, compared to the homologous versions from Table 9. In contradiction with the overall trend, the LN-4VF model registered a deterioration in its final accuracy. Regarding the RAFR plots, it can be seen that with the VFM loss normalization all the models achieved a correct force reconstruction at the initial time stages, for all the specimens, independently of the number of virtual fields. In general, the LN-4VF model starts to deteriorate in performance with significant scatter in later stages, while the remaining models achieve smoother curves, albeit with some deviations still present. These results are in line with the conclusions taken from Fig. 16 at the beginning of this section. Nonetheless, the normalization seems cause a slight degradation in the RAFR on the plastic stages, particularly for the D and Sigma specimens, with the latter showing the same kind of results as previously discussed.

6.4. Stress reconstruction

In this section, the best performing model, LN-12VF trained with the normalized VFM loss, was selected to evaluate the quality of the corresponding stress reconstruction on different mechanical specimens.

6.4.1. Mechanical test with cruciform specimen

The virtual experiment based on the cruciform specimen, with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, was chosen as an example from the validation dataset. The contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 124$) of the virtual experiment are shown in Fig. 18. It can be seen that the LN-12VF model approximates the FEA solution quite well, exhibiting low absolute errors across the specimen, for all the stress components. In general, the highest error magnitudes correspond to key regions around the fillets near the central hole and on one of the sides of the arms of the specimen. On the latter regions, the white blobs indicate a tendency to substantially underestimate the stress, particularly for on the x - and y - directions. Along the circumference of the central hole, there are small areas denoted by black blobs that indicate a slight overestimation happening for all the stress components. Although this specimen is not rich in shear information, surprisingly, the model performs the best when predicting the shear stress, exhibiting the lowest absolute errors for that component. For the stresses along the x - and y - directions the model shows very similar performance.

Fig. 16. RAFR along the length (in mm) of the three heterogeneous uniaxial specimens for the selected models. The ideal value is denoted by the dashed horizontal line, and the grey area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$. For the S specimen, the vertical dashed lines indicate the location of each notch root.

6.4.2. Mechanical test with D specimen

The contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 143$) of the virtual experiment based on the D specimen are shown in Fig. 19. This specimen was not part of the training data and is considered to be the more complex, however, the results indicate the LN-12VF is able to predict the stress fields in good agreement with the FEA solution, capturing the major features and symmetries of the stress fields. The results show, in general, low mean and median absolute errors across the entire ROI for all the stress components. Particularly for the stress in the x -direction and the shear stress, the model exhibits a slight tendency to overestimate their magnitudes on specific zones along the left circular edge of the ROI, which show more subtle gradients on the reference solution. The model seems to struggle when evaluating the stress tensor on a key area near the lower region of the small interior notch, resulting in the highest absolute errors. There is a notable underestimation of the stress in the y -direction on left circular edge of the specimen, evidenced by the white blob over that region. Once again, the model performs the best when predicting the shear stress, as shown by the lower absolute errors for this component.

Fig. 17. RAFR along the length (in mm) of the heterogeneous uniaxial specimens, for the models trained with the normalized VFM loss. The ideal value is denoted by a dashed line, and the grey area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$. For the S specimen, the vertical dashed lines indicate the location of each notch root.

6.4.3. Mechanical test with S specimen

The contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 121$) of the virtual experiment based on the S specimen are shown in Fig. 20. This specimen was also not included in the training dataset. The results indicate the LN-12VF is able to predict stress fields that closely match the FEA solution, perfectly capturing the main features of the stress fields. The error maps show low mean and median absolute errors across the entire ROI, for all the stress components, and lower maximum absolute errors compared to the D specimen, which could be attributed to the lower complexity of the S specimen. For the stresses along x - and y -directions, there is a tendency to slightly underestimate the stress in a small region near the root of both notches, which is the area of maximum absolute error. In contrast, for the shear stress, the model tends to overestimate the stress on that region of the ROI.

Fig. 18. Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_t = 124$ of the virtual experiment, based on the cruciform specimen, with boundary conditions $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm. Comparison between the FEA solution and the LN-12VF model predictions with corresponding absolute difference.

6.4.4. Mechanical test with Sigma specimen

The contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 121$) of the virtual experiment based on the Sigma specimen are shown in Fig. 21. This specimen was also not part of the training data. The results show that the LN-12VF predicts stress fields in good agreement with the FEA solution, capturing the main features of each stress field and the major symmetries, particularly for the shear component. In general, the results show low mean and median absolute errors across the entire ROI, for all the stress components. The model struggles to predict the stresses on the regions around the central zone of the specimen, with stress being underestimated in areas with lower magnitudes and overestimated in the areas of higher magnitude. The effect is particularly visible on the shear stress. The maximum absolute errors also originate from these specific regions. The component x-direction seems to be affected to a lesser extent, showing the lowest absolute errors across the board.

6.5. FEA implementation

The experiment based on the cruciform specimen with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm was rerun with the UMAT implementation of the LN-12VF model. The resulting contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 124$) are compared with the reference, as shown in Fig. 22, with the corresponding absolute error. In general, the UMAT implementation of the LN-12VF model is capable of capturing the main features of the stress fields in good agreement with the reference, with low absolute errors in line with the results obtained during inference shown in Fig. 18. The highest error magnitudes correspond to the same key regions around the fillets near the central hole and on both sides of the arms of the specimen. Once again, the model seems to perform better while predicting the shear component, despite the original training dataset being poor in shear states. These results show that the UMAT implementation of the LN-12VF achieves similar results to the ones obtained during inference, confirming an accurate implementation without issues.

Fig. 19. Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_i = 143$ of the virtual experiment based on the D specimen. Comparison between the FEA solution and the LN-12VF model predictions with corresponding absolute difference.

Fig. 20. Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_i = 121$ of the virtual experiment based on the S specimen. Comparison between the FEA solution and the LN-12VF model predictions with corresponding absolute difference.

Fig. 21. Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_i = 121$ of the virtual experiment based on the Sigma specimen. Comparison between the FEA solution and the LN-12VF model predictions with corresponding absolute difference.

Fig. 22. Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_t = 124$ of the virtual experiment, based on the cruciform specimen, with boundary conditions $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm. Comparison between the FEA solution and the UMAT implementation of the LN-12VF model with corresponding absolute difference.

7. Concluding remarks

The current paper capitalized on the findings of the previous two papers of the authors to train a GRU-based RNN with the VFM from scratch, without labelled data. A new and improved neural network architecture was adopted, employing residual connections to improve the gradient flow and stabilize the training dynamic. A hyperparameter tuning allowed to optimize the model even further by identifying the best combination of a select set of hyperparameters.

In general, the learning curves show stable training dynamics for all the models, even though the training was performed without labelled data, relying only on the VFM loss and the physics-based constraints. The test loss curves indicated a slight tendency to overfit when specific sets of virtual fields were used. A sensitivity analysis has shown that the predictive accuracy is highly correlated with the number of virtual fields, with the models trained with larger sets of virtual fields achieving lower RMSE metric on the validation set. The same also applies to the force reconstruction, with the RAFR plots showing that models trained with seven or more virtual fields were able to achieve a more accurate correct reconstruction, except for the initial (elastic) time stages. However, this issue was addressed with a proper VFM loss normalization, which has shown to improve the accuracy of force reconstruction, for all the models, across all the time stages.

The stress contour plots show predictions in good agreement with the reference solution, with residual median and average absolute errors. Nevertheless, in very specific zones of the specimens, the models seem to over- or under-predict the stresses resulting in high maximum errors being registered on those areas. Further validation studies were conducted considering the incorporation of the best-performing model into a FEA solver. In this context, the model shows very similar results for both inference and the UMAT version, confirming an accurate implementation without issues.

These findings show that the VFM is effectively deemed feasible for neural network training. More importantly, this indirect training methodology using unlabelled data is proven to provide robust results, on par with labelled training approaches. Nonetheless, the results show that there is margin for further improvement. For example, using the ReLU function instead of the ReLU6 would allow for the penalty terms to have stronger effect, which could result in improved final accuracy. However, the ReLU being unbounded caused the training to be unstable. The universe of training data could also be enhanced with the introduction of data from a specimen richer in shear states and/or data from classical homogeneous tests such as tensile, shear or bulge tests.

Within the context of validation, the RAFR provided invaluable insights during model selection and allowed to identify a key area of improvement, thus the authors highlight once again the importance of incorporating external KPIs into the validation workflow.

The proposed modelling methodology represents a significant departure from the state-of-the-art by introducing the coupling between the VFM and RNNs for indirect training. The approach relies only on measurable force and displacement/deformation data, which makes it particularly advantageous for experimental settings where stress data is unavailable. Ultimately, the method's disruptive nature lies in its ability to completely bypass the complex inverse parameter identification process.

Two compelling strengths of the modelling methodology hereby presented are the computational efficiency offered by the VFM, since it does not rely on FEA for further calculations, and the fact that it does not require modelling complex experimental boundary conditions. Moreover, the way the method was devised offers a seamless integration into the emerging Material Testing 2.0 (MT2.0) paradigm, ensuring the compatibility with both experimental DIC data and numerically generated datasets. Another key advantage is the flexibility provided by ANNs, which can effectively handle large volumes of training data and be retrained for different materials within the same class, without requiring explicit modifications to the underlying model structure.

The method's robustness is reinforced by the GRU-based RNN with residual connections, which mitigate vanishing gradients and improve training stability. Additionally, the incorporation of physics-based constraints ensures thermodynamic consistency and prevents unphysical responses. The method has also demonstrated a strong generalization capability, when validated against different heterogeneous mechanical tests. Moreover, the assessment based on the RAFR KPI provides a benchmark not only in terms of predictive accuracy but also in terms of physical consistency.

Nevertheless, as a newly introduced approach in this field, several key areas require further refinement and development. One major challenge is ensuring the physical correctness of the stress predictions. Although the integration of physics-based constraints partially addresses this issue, further improvements are necessary to guarantee stronger adherence to the fundamental physical principles across diverse material behaviours. Furthermore, the accuracy and convergence of the training process remain highly dependent on the choice of virtual fields, which, if poorly selected, may lead to suboptimal learning and predictive accuracy, requiring additional tuning. Another significant limitation comes from the fact that the VFM is limited to 2D analysis. Therefore, the proposed method is not directly applicable to scenarios where the test specimen may experience out-of-plane deformation, which would require a full 3D modelling approach (e.g. FEMU), restricting its applicability in certain experimental setups. Moreover, while the method eliminates the need for FEA during training, its integration into FEM solvers still requires additional validation to ensure numerical. Lastly, selecting appropriate network architectures, loss penalty factors, and virtual fields can be quite demanding. Unless some level of automation is introduced, this step could remain a bottleneck in the practical adoption of the methodology.

In conclusion, while the proposed approach offers a paradigm shift in data-driven constitutive modelling by combining the VFM with RNNs for indirect training, it also presents several challenges that need to be addressed in future developments. Once fully matured, its ability to bypass the inverse parameter identification process, its computational efficiency, and its seamless integration within the MT2.0 framework could make it a transformative tool for both experimental and numerical material characterization.

Disclaimer

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Rúben Lourenço: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Petia Georgieva:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources. **A. Andrade-Campos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Ruben Lourenco reports financial support was provided by Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology. Ruben Lourenco reports financial support and travel were provided by Research Fund for Coal and Steel. A. Andrade-Campos reports financial support, administrative support, equipment, drugs, or supplies, and travel were provided by Research Fund for Coal and Steel. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Sigmoid-weighted linear units

The Sigmoid-weighted linear unit (SiLU) is smooth, approximately equal to the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) for large activations z_k and approximately zero for large negative activations (see Fig. A.23(a)). Unlike the ReLU function, the SiLU is differentiable at $z_k = 0$ and admits a global minimum (-0.28 at $z_k \approx 1.28$). The latter acts as a “soft floor” for the weights and introduces a regularizing effect avoiding learning weights with large magnitudes. The first derivative of the SiLU (dSiLU) has a shape similar to the sigmoid (see Fig. A.23(b)), albeit steeper and with some overshoot [74].

Fig. A.23. Plots for the (a) SiLU and ReLU activation functions and (b) the corresponding derivatives dSiLU, dReLU, compared to the Sigmoid activation.

Appendix B. User-defined virtual fields

Fig. B.24. Contour plots of virtual displacements considered for training - part I.

Fig. B.25. Contour plots of the virtual displacements considered for training - part II.

Fig. B.26. Contour plots of the virtual strains corresponding to the full set of virtual displacements considered for training.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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